

Proceedings of
Two Day National Conference

on

Materials and their Applications: A Broad Perspective

9th-10th January 2020

at

Thorale Bajirao Peshwe Sabhagruha, Thane

Organized by

Vidya Prasarak Mandal's

B.N. Bandodkar College of Science, Thane

- FIST 'O' Level Grant (2013-14)
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Contents

1.	Nanoscience and Nanotechnology for harvesting Solar Energy <i>C. S. Gopinath</i>	1
2.	Metal Oxide Materials for Multifunctional Applications <i>Parasharam M. Shirage</i>	2
3.	Nano-phase Luminescent Materials for Sustainable Development <i>S. K. Omanwar</i>	3
4.	Studies on Bilayer Thin Film Magnetolectric Composites <i>Prof. N. Venkatramani</i>	4
5.	“Material research at SAMEER, Mumbai” <i>Alok Verma</i>	5
6.	Formation of Functional Oxides and Their Use in Energy Generation and Storage <i>Deepa Khushalani</i>	6
7.	Spintronic Materials and Devices - A New Avenue <i>Rajeev Shesha Joshi</i>	7
8.	Review of Terahertz (THz) Spectroscopy and THz Studies of Metamaterials <i>S. S. Prabhu</i>	8
9.	Advanced Magnetic Materials and their Applications <i>K. G. Suresh</i>	9
10.	Moringa Leaves: Synthesis of Biomaterial and Its Application <i>Anita S. Goswami-Giri, Jagdish B. Kudav, Anjali A. Yadav, Pooja J. Singh and Sumit R. Singh</i>	10
11.	NO ₂ gas Sensing Properties of ZnO Thin Film Prepared by Sol-gel Method <i>K. V. Madhale, B.N.Jamadar, A. R. Nimbalkar, N. B. Patil and S. B. Kulkarni</i>	15
12.	Synthesis and Study of Carbon Quantum Dots Using Facile Oven Assisted Carbonization Method <i>Samiksha Pandey, Soni Yadav and V. Raikwar</i>	19
13.	Molecular Interaction Studies in Binary Liquid Mixtures of Allyl Amine (AA) and 2-Methoxy Ethanol (2ME) from Ultrasonic Studies and IR Spectroscopy <i>Sangita S. Meshram, Bhalchandra K. Mandlekar, Umakant B. Tumberphale and Prashant G. Gawli</i>	23
14.	Synthesis and Fluorescence Properties of Eu ³⁺ to Eu ²⁺ in BaAl ₂ Si ₂ O ₈ Phosphor under Charcoal Atmosphere <i>U. B. Gokhe, K. A. Koparkar and S. K. Omanwar</i>	29
15.	Synthesis and Characterization of Manganese Cobaltite as Electrode Material for Supercapacitor Application <i>Snehal Kadam, Pavan Khadekar, Harshita Shenoy, Ganesh Nagarvani, Jayshri Patil, Nidhi Tiwari, Abhishek Kakade, Rahul Ingole and Shrinivas B. Kulkarni</i>	35
16.	Plastic Peril on Species Diversity and Fish Catch: A Zone-wise Comparative Assessment between Ulhas River Estuary and Thane Creek <i>Sudesh Rathod</i>	40
17.	Synthesis and Characterization of CdSSe Thin Films Synthesized by Varying Deposition Temperatures <i>Cephas A. Vanderhyde and Hemangi A. Raut</i>	47
18.	Dielectric, Magneto-dielectric and Magnetic Properties of x[Co _{0.9} Ni _{0.1} Fe ₂ O ₄](1-x)[0.5Ba _{0.7} Ca _{0.3} TiO ₃ -0.5BaZr _{0.2} Ti _{0.8} O ₃]Multiferroic Composite <i>Abhishek Kakade and Dr. S. B. Kulkarni</i>	54
19.	Study of Dielectric and Magneto-dielectric Properties of x[Co _{0.9} Ni _{0.1} Fe ₂ O ₄](1-x)[Ba(Zr _{0.2} Ti _{0.8})O ₃]Multiferroic Composite <i>Abhishek Yadav, Santosh Shinde, Sarthak Hajirnis, Kiran Gaikwad, Abhishek Kakade and Dr. S. B. Kulkarni</i>	54

Plastic Peril on Species Diversity and Fish Catch: A Zone-wise Comparative Assessment between Ulhas River Estuary and Thane Creek

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Abstract : The anthropogenic activities prevalent in the Ulhas River estuary and the Thane creek were accentuated to correlate with their zone wise plastic pollution with that of existent artisanal fisheries status. The observation revealed that there is rise in plastic peril with increased anthropogenic activities which caused depletion in the fisheries of the ambient water bodies to non-profitable level. This consequently decreased the fishing activities. At 80% Bray-Curtis similarity resemblance in PCO showed that UZ-II, UZ-III and TZ-III were similar at 87.7% ordination in fish species abundance whereas UZ-III and TZ-III were similar at 89% ordination in biomass. The pattern of fish catches were in accordance with zone-wise deterioration level due to the impact of plastic peril which revealed direct correlation to that of dwindling status of the fisheries of the ambient water bodies.

Keywords : Plastic pollution, Ulhas River estuary, Thane creek, anthropogenic activities, fisheries status, abundance, diversity, biomass, catches, PCO ordination, Bray-Curtis Similarity Matrix.

Introduction

Thane City is a connecting land-mass amongst the sub-urban Thane, urban Mumbai and Vashi (New Mumbai) located in the Maharashtra State of India. Mumbai-Thane-Vashi complex could be considered as one of the most populous 'megacity' comprised of more than 10 billion population and stands as 4th most populous city in the world. The Thane city is well known for its high residential clusters, fostering the requisite manpower to the corporate systems of Mumbai and Navi Mumbai, owing to which hitherto, a considerable portion of forest and non-residential land has been mutated to suit the residential developments. Besides, the 'Thane-Belapur industrial belt' has been recognized as largest industrial cluster in the Asia (Zingde and Govindan, 2001) along with numerous industries located at Kalyan-Dombivli, Thane City proper and Bhiwandi (Qamrul, 1980) areas of the Thane district. The Thane City is therefore subjected to a high anthropogenic stress, lest, it exceeds the carrying capacity of the prevailing urban ecosystem.

The Ulhas River estuary and the Thane creek are the major inward waters located in the vicinity of the Thane City. The Ulhas River estuary (URE) commences from S-E near Dombivli regions upstream between latitude 19° 14' 43" N and longitude 16° 06' 59" E; meanders for about 40 km before it joins the Arabian Sea towards N-W at Vasai (Bassein) creek situated between the latitude 18° 45' to 19° 19', N and longitude

Fig 1: Map Showing study zones of URE and TC

73° 21' to 72° 45', E on the world map. The Thane creek (TC) runs downstream from Balkum to the Mankurd-Vashi bridge towards the east side of the Thane City. The mouth of the creek opens towards its S-W approach to Mumbai harbor bay in the Arabian Sea between Latitude 19° 01' N and Longitude 72° 58' E and heads northwards for about 26 km to join the URE at Balkum towards N-W between latitude 19° 13' N and longitude 73° 00' E on world map. Thane Creek has lesser influence of fresh water as it connects to URE with a narrow connection at upstream with feeble fresh water influx from URE during monsoon thus remaining as *euhaline* for the major part of the year. However, it is highly influenced by storm waters from

in monsoon and urban activities (industrial, domestic, civil and cultural activities) from Thane City proper.

The two dynamic aquatic environments viz. URE and TC situated in the vicinity of the Mumbai-Thane complex are the major water bodies supporting the local fisher folks for their livelihood from many decades (Rathod, 2002). Both the ambient water bodies are known historically for their various records of lucrative fisheries (Mutsaddi, 1964; Qamrul, 1980; Tandel, 1984; Pejaver, 1984). These have turned down to be non-productive in the recent years due to the pollution pressure exerted by industrial and urban activities (Rathod, 2005).

Plastic Menace: Presently with the increased use of plastic is disposed in huge amount near shores. About 80% of the material is plastic which is non-degradable and provokes smothering. Entangling and drowning of biota (birds, mammals) may happen and inflict physical injury to animals (turtles) or even an obstruction of digestive system after ingestion of plastic objects. Once in the food-web, plastics release toxic substances. Containers or all sorts (bottles, boxes) will host alien species and help in the transportation of invasive species (Abu El-Magd and Hermas, 2010). These ultimately get into the coastal waters and pollute them and also get carried to open oceans. Besides, large gyres (vortexes) in the oceans trap floating plastic debris. The North Pacific Gyre for example has collected the so-called “Great Pacific Garbage Patch” that is now estimated at 100 times the size of Texas. Many of these long-lasting pieces wind up in the stomachs of marine birds and animals. This results in obstruction of digestive pathways which leads to reduced appetite or even starvation.

URE and TC are also highly impacted due to solid wastes, most of them were found to be of non-biodegradable type (Rathod, 2005 & 2016; Singare, 2012). Recently, the use of plastic with regard to packaging and handling of the goods has amplified several folds. The extensive uses of plastic in urbanized areas like Thane City pose high hazards to the aquatic environment in the vicinity. However, there is no appropriate disposal system available to manage the huge plastic garbage generated daily in the city, till date. The domestic plastic waste is casually discarded along with degradable garbage and is dumped without sorting on the solid waste disposal land-fills. This plastic waste

is ultimately carried along with the land run-off to the waters of URE and TC during the monsoon. Several kinds of non-biodegradable elements viz. carry bags, milk and oil bags, plastic bottles, poly-foam fibres, polystyrene, foot wares, automobile tyres and tubes were observed along URE and TC during the present study. Moreover, it is of common scenario that the disposals of plastic in the ambient water bodies are customary practices or some ritual activities. The plastic disposal are often increased during the rituals practices like Idol immersion; ‘nirmalya’ immersion; ‘naralipournima’ immersion; and ‘asthi-visarjan’ frequented in the ambient waters in the vicinity of Thane city. Ironically, it is customary to dispose the remains of these worships or rituals in plastic bags along URE and TC. TC is a semi-isolated water body with narrow channel as compared to URE. Whereas URE not only possesses a wider channel but also is benefited by riverine fresh water flow from upper stretches.

Fishing activities were high until 1996 when Vashi-Mankhurd Bridge was constructed on harbor railway line which narrowed the orifice of the creek (Rathod, 2016). Probably the narrowing of orifice caused hindrance to the water currents during tidal movements (Sandilyan & Kathiresan, 2012; Joshi & Kale, 2013). As a result the creek water was unable to be flushed completely hence retaining plastic within creek for long and allowing it to accumulate. It was reported by fishermen that nets were inoperable in plastic laden water in entire TZ-I and TZ-II. It was reported that the plastic can affect the feeding sites of the fish (Sandilyan & Kathiresan, 2012; Joshi & Kale, 2013). Also catches were reduced to non-profitable level in the subsequent years after 1996. Consequently, it was observed that the fishing attempts were negligible in these zones (Rathod, 2016).

Materials and methods

Each study area was divided into three zones on the basis of demographic and urban characteristics viz. upper zone (Z-I), middle zone (Z-II) and lower zone (Z-III). The two ambient water bodies were divided as follows (Table 1):

Table 1: Demarcation of zones in URE and TC

Sr. No.	Water body	Zone	Characteristics	Areas included
1	URE	UZ-I	Highly residential; influenced by industrial clusters of Dombivli and agricultural fields from the catchment; immersion practices frequent	Kalyan, Dombivli, Kharegaon, Balkumon south bank and Anjurdive, Anjur, Mankoli, Alimghar and Dive on north bank. (length: 12.4 km)
		UZ-II	Sparse residential areas; impacted majorly by sand excavation activities and Bhiwandi industrial areas; agricultural fields and solid waste disposal moderate; immersion practices rare	Balkum, Waghbil, Mograpada, Nagla and Gaimukh occurred on south bank while Bhiwandi, Kasheli, Kalher, Kevani-Dive, Kalwar, Dunge, Kharbao and Paigaon on north bank. (length: 12.7 km)
		UZ-III	Highly residential; sand excavation activities; fishing activities; immersion practices frequent	Gaimukh jetty, Retibandar, Ghodbandar and Mira-Bhayandar areas (length: 10.9 km)
2	TC	TZ-I	Highly residential; influenced by industrial clusters of Wagale estate and Vitawa-Airoli; salt pans; immersion practices frequent	Thane city. Vitawa, Airoli on east bank and Mulund, Bhandup, Vikhroli on west bank
		TZ-II	Highly residential; influenced by industrial clusters of Airoli-Ghansoli immersion practices frequent	Airoli, Ghansoli on east bank and Vikhroli, Ghatkopar on west bank
		TZ-III	Highly residential; influenced by industrial clusters of Ghansoli-Vashi; salt pans; immersion practices frequent	Koparkhairne, Vashi on east bank and Sion to Trombay on west bank

On site observation was carried out to study the anthropogenic activities imparting the threat due to plastic pollution along the entire stretches of URE and TC. The ambient water bodies contained number of point and non-point sources of plastic disposal. The hot-spots such as domestic clusters, solid waste disposal spots (point sources of plastic disposal), occasions of routine practices or some ritual activities viz. idol immersion (God Ganesh visarjan, Goddess Gauri

visarjan and Goddess Durga visarjan), 'nirmalya'¹ disposal, 'naralipournima'² offerings and 'asthi-visarjan' (non-point sources of plastic disposal) were observed and recorded on field. URE was found with total 6 and TC was with total 9 plastic dumping grounds (point sources). Ranks were allotted to the dumping ground based on their size. The fisheries were recorded qualitatively and quantitatively, on site, at various landing

¹'Nirmalya' is the process of disposing the remains of worship ('pooja') or rituals like idol immersion and funeral ('asthi-visarjan'). These activities cause large amount of plastic and polystyrene disposal in the ambient waters.

²'Naralipournima' is an important festival celebrated majorly by Hindus in the western coastal regions of India. Also known as 'Coconut Day' observed on the 'Pournima' (full moon day) in the month of 'Shravana' according to the Hindu calendar. Fishermen community along URE and TC celebrates this festival to ward off untoward incidents while sailing in the sea during which along with the offerings in worships huge amount of polythene bags are disposed.

centers along URE and TC and also from the local fish markets such as Vashi, Ghansoli, Koparkhairne, Airoli, Thane, Kalwa, Vitava, Kharegaon, Anjur, Alimghar, Mankoli, Kalher, Kevani-Diva, Gaimukh and Mira-Bhainder. Specimens were collected from these landing centers or markets and identified using keys given in 'Fishes of India', (Day, 1883) and FAO sheets.

Result and Discussion

Massive plastic dumping spots and disposal were concurred along both URE and TC (Fig. 2 a & b). It was observed that in URE, UZ-II a huge solid waste dumping was allowed by Thane Municipal Corporation. The satellite images on google earth from 2004 to 2015 revealed tremendous impact on mangrove in the vicinity due to solid waste dumping. Moreover, in TC, TZ-I

and TZ-II possessed higher amount of plastic. Several places the mangrove pneumatophores were tangled with plastic. The plastic debris were carried by tidal currents were formed into piles at certain places. At some instances the fishes, especially young ones of mudskippers were found smothering due to plastic (Fig. 2). It was observed that the TC hindered tidal-water flushing action which restricted the plastic material from escaping to ocean resulting in its accumulation (Kantharajan *et al.* 2018). The accumulated plastic could also velocity of tidal oscillations. Fish landings of 'Dol' net (a stationary bag net) catches from TZ-III contained huge amount of plastic. Fishers had to invest considerable amount of time for separating plastic from landings (Fig. 2, c-i).

Figure 2: Some solid waste dumping grounds spotted along URE and TC and their impact

Solid waste dumping at - (a) Huge plastic dumping and sorting near Kharegaon, UZ-I (b) Medium Solid waste dumping near Mahagiri, TZ-I

Plastic at Vashi in T-ZIII (ci); Young ones of mudskippers trapped in plastic (cii) in UZ-I and plastic clogging the roots of mangroves in TZ-I (ciii), near Mahagiri, Thane City

Total 5 out of 6 dumping grounds (point sources) on URE and 6 out of 9 on TC were large in size. Apart from these point sources there are several non-point sources of plastic disposal as stated earlier. URE scored 48 and TC 144 ranks according to their possible impact due to former point sources. Zonal impact of plastic was greater in TC as compared to that of URE. TZ-I and TZ-II were highest in ranks. TC scored higher in plastic pollution ranks (Table 2).

Table 2: Ranks allotted on the basis of number and size of plastic dumping along URE and TC

Plastic menace: Plastic was a great concern in the ambient waters, specifically in TC. There were several hotspots of plastic accumulation on URE and TC	URE	Number	Ranks	TC	umber	Ranks
	UZ-I	3	24	TZ-I	5	80
	UZ-II	1	8	TZ-II	3	48
	UZ-III	2	16	TZ-III	1	16
	Total→	6	48	Total→	9	144

The data of fish species abundance and fish catches in biomass were transformed to square root before obtaining resemblance matrix with Bray-Curtis Similarity. PCO was run with Permanova. Also the dendrograms were obtained with agglomerative cluster analysis of plastic pollution ranks in Primer version6 software. The dendrogram was then overlaid separately on PCOs for species abundance and biomass (Fig.3, a & b) respectively to reveal the similarity.

Figure 3: Zonal Fish Species Abundance (a) and Biomass (b) in URE and TC

The PCO ordination of zonal fish species abundance (a) and fish biomass (b) with overlay of the dendrogram of Bray-Curtis similarity agglomeration clusters of 40 to 80 percent of similarity of rankings on plastic pressure. The PCO varimax ordination of species abundance represented strongly at 87.8% while that of biomass represented strongly at 89% of variation. Highest species abundance was revealed in UZII, UZIII and TZIII; average in UZI whereas TZI and TZII showed lowest. The fish catches (biomass) ordination revealed that TZIII and UZIII were highest; UZI and UZIII were average; TZII lower while TZI was poorest.

It is evident that the fish catches depleted significantly in these zones in present study. TZ-I and TZ-II were lowest in fish abundance (Fig. 3a) and biomass (Fig. 3b). UZ-III, UZ-II and TZ-III were similar in abundance at 80% Bray-Curtis similarity resemblance (Fig. 3a). Whereas, catches (biomass) depicted highest in UZ-III and TZ-III whilst lowest in TZ-I and TZ-II in present study (Fig. 3b). This confirmed that TZ-I and TZ-II were highly disturbed due to plastic pollution. Although UZ-II, UZ-III and TZ-III revealed similarity in species abundance, UZ-II being average in fish catch as that of UZ-I. Overall Thane creek was highly disturb due to plastic peril. This might be due to the lack of complete flushing of creek water to ocean. The mass of plastic in the creek also impacting on the velocity of tidal oscillations which hindered the creek water. However it is evident that Ulhas River Estuary was benefited due to riverine flow and comparatively broader channel which allowed complete flushing of the tidal water and hence the condition remained better. This relieved the plastic pressure in URE intermittently and sustained better fisheries status.

Conclusion:

Plastic played important role to define the fish species abundance and biomass in the present study. Upper zones of TC viz. TZ-I and TZ-II were highly depleted

with fisheries due to various anthropogenic activities causing plastic hazard. Oceanic segments of both URE and TC were high in fish abundance and catches. Whilst the upper regions which were disturbed due to profound anthropogenic activities causing plastic pollution were very low in fish species diversity as well as biomass discerning the direct relation with the levels of plastic peril in the ambient water bodies.

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